

Yellow Mealworm Larvae Derived Eco-Friendly Substrates for Responsible Electronics

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The growth of the electrical and electronic industries has led to an inevitable increase in e-waste, posing potential risks to human health. To mitigate this issue, eco-friendly and biocompatible substrates derived from food-based materials can offer a sustainable alternative for responsible electronic circuit integration, helping to reduce e-waste. In this study, a yellow mealworm larva (YML)-based substrate is proposed, aligning with the principles of green electronics. The prepared substrate is characterized using FTIR, SEM, Optical microscopy, water contact angle analysis, TGA, and dielectric properties measurements. To evaluate the biodegradability of YML substrate, comprehensive studies are performed, including moisture absorption rate, water degradation rate, and soil degradation rate, providing a thoughtful study of its environmental breakdown behavior. The dielectric properties (dielectric constant, dielectric loss) and resistivity of the substrate are thoroughly evaluated for the YML substrate. The results demonstrate favorable thermal and electrical properties. As a proof-of-concept, LC electrical circuits are fabricated using the YML-based substrate and compared with the commercially available substrates (FR4), to assess its suitability for electronic applications. The developed YML substrates show strong potential for use in RF and high-frequency electronic circuit applications, maintaining consistent performance even under fluctuating environmental conditions.

1. Introduction

The production of electrical and electronic equipment has been one of the fastest-growing industries worldwide over the past few decades.^[1] The global electronics market is projected to expand by 30% in the coming years, with an estimated value of USD 990 billion by 2027.^[2] However, this increased production will inevitably lead to a rise in e-waste. According to a report by the United Nations Environment Programme, annual e-waste production has reached 50 million tonnes, with only 20% being reused or recycled.^[2] The majority of e-waste is either disposed of in landfills or informally refurbished. Printed circuit boards (PCBs) represent one of the largest contributors to e-waste, originating from computers, televisions, and mobile devices.^[1,3,4] PCB-related e-waste contains hazardous substances such as brominated flame retardants, glass fibers, heavy metals, and epoxy resins. These substances are difficult to recycle and pose significant human and environmental risks.^[5-7]

The rapid growth of the computer industry is also a significant contributor to the increasing volume of e-waste. Millions of computers are decommissioned each year.^[8,9] The e-waste contains both valuable materials and hazardous substances. To mitigate health risks and reduce environmental strain, specialized e-waste handling and management are essential. While e-waste recycling offers a promising solution for recovering precious materials, challenges such as high labor costs, inadequate facilities, and strict environmental regulations hinder large-scale implementation.^[10]

Recent research has emphasized the need to replace hazardous thermosetting polymers with biodegradable and biomaterial-based alternatives. Biomaterial-based electronics offer the potential to achieve zero PCB waste.^[6] Various biomaterials, including bio-plastics, hydrogels, gelatine, polylactic acid (PLA), mycelium, and cellulose, have been explored for electronic application.^[3,11-15] Yellow mealworm larvae (YML) have also emerged as promising biomaterials for electronic applications due to their favorable electrical and thermal properties.^[16-18] Although existing studies highlight numerous materials with

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Figure 1. Schematic representations of a) the preparation process for YML powder, b) the mixture of YML powder with gelatine in water, and c) the photograph of the prepared substrates.

potential for biomaterials-inspired electronics, some limitations require further investigation and analysis to support large-scale adoption. For instance, hydrogels doped with organic food extracts^[11] often contain compounds that degrade over time, reducing the shelf life and reliability of circuits. Similarly, while superior biodegradable blends of poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA)^[12] and fungal mycelium^[13] show promise, their lower thermal stability compared to traditional PCB materials presents challenges, such as difficulty in withstanding classical soldering. These materials also exhibit relatively low adhesion and compatibility with conductive inks or metallic traces. Plasticized gelatine films are limited by their hygroscopic nature and susceptibility to moisture-induced degradation.^[14] Addressing these material limitations is essential to minimize the environmental and health impacts of PCB waste. In addition to electronics, YML-based materials have the potential as edible substrates for medical applications in both humans and animals.^[16,18] However, there remains a gap in research focused on their electronic applications, highlighting the need for further exploration in this area.

In this work, we advance the state of the art in biodegradable and bio-derived electronic materials by developing yellow mealworm larvae-based substrates as an alternative to conventional PCB substrates. The motivation for this study stems from the desire to enhance the circular economy principle by reducing waste and utilizing scalable, renewable raw materials. The fabricated substrates exhibit unique material properties, being

lightweight and potentially more flexible than traditional materials, while maintaining stability in environments with varying moisture levels. Comprehensive material analysis, including Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), optical microscopy, water contact angle measurements, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), environmental durability test, and dielectric properties evaluation, confirmed the substrate's superior dielectric performance, as well as robust thermal, and mechanical properties. To further enhance the physical and mechanical characteristics, gelatine was included in the processing of the prepared YML substrates. As a result, the proposed biodegradable material can serve as either a rigid or flexible substrate for electronic circuit design, with its thickness tunable to meet specific application requirements.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Preparation of Yellow Mealworm Larvae (YML) Powder

The yellow mealworm larvae (*Tenebrio molitor*) used in the bioassay were bred at the Laboratory of Entomology at the Faculty of Agriculture at the University of Novi Sad, Serbia. The breeding process began with 10-day-old adult insects, which were placed on a food substrate composed of 80% wheat bran, 15% ground rolled oats, and 5% brewer's yeast. The substrate was evenly spread in standard plastic insect-rearing trays, measuring 8 cm ×

Figure 2. a) FTIR spectra of YML substrate, b) variation in water contact angle over a 300 s duration of YML substrate with a thickness of 2 mm, c) Phases of thermal degradation analysis (TGA and DTG) of the prepared YML substrate, d) SEM images of the YML substrate at higher magnification, e) SEM images of the YML substrate at lower magnification, f) an optical microscopy image of the YML substrate.

50 cm × 60 cm. The trays were kept in a climate-controlled chamber (Witeg Thermostable GC 450) set to 26 ± 1 °C and 60% relative humidity. The adult insects remained on the food mixture for 7 days to facilitate mating and egg-laying. After this period, the adults were removed, and the trays were returned to the climate chamber to allow the eggs to complete embryogenesis and hatch into larvae. Fresh apple slices were provided three times per week to ensure adequate moisture for the larvae. On days 35

and 65 post-adult removal, the food substrate was sieved and replaced with a fresh mixture. The full rearing cycle lasted 90 days, after which the larvae were sieved and transferred to new trays for a 24-hour starvation period. Following starvation, the larvae were cleaned and blanched for 180 s. Following blanching, the larvae were drained and placed on drying racks, which were then transferred to a laboratory convective dryer (Memmert AX60) set at 65 °C for 24 h. Once dried, the larvae were ground using a laboratory mill (IKA MultiDrive basic) to produce worm powder. The powder was sieved through a series of sieves with openings ranging from 0.50 mm to 1.00 mm. For this study, the fine particles that passed through the 0.50 mm sieve were selected for the fabrication of electronic substrates. **Figure 1a** displays the procedure applied to prepare YML powder.

2.2. Preparation of Substrate

To prepare rigid and flexible electronic substrates, YML powder (10 mg) and gelatine (1 g) were added to 60 mL water. The mixture was heated at a low temperature (40–60 °C) and continuously stirred to prevent lump formation. The prepared mixture was then poured onto a clean, level casting mold or surface and evenly spread to form uniform films. The films were dried in the laboratory convector at 25 °C for 48 h to produce flexible substrates, and for 72 h to create rigid substrates. Once dried, the films were carefully peeled from the mold. The substrate thickness can be controlled by maintaining precise environmental conditions during drying (25 °C, 58%RH)

Figure 3. The moisture absorption rate (MAR) of YML substrate.

as well as the shape and diameter of the mold. Figure 1b,c display the procedure applied to fabricate substrates from Yellow Mealworm Larvae and the photograph of prepared substrates, respectively.

2.3. Experimental Setup

The electrical properties of the as-prepared YML substrates were measured using an impedance analyzer (HIOKI, IM 7585). The electrical characterization of the YML substrate was performed using a parallel plate capacitor (PPC) configuration. The capacitor consisted of two circular aluminum thin-film electrodes, each with a diameter of 2.6 cm. To confirm precise control over the measurement conditions, the bottom electrode was fixed, while the top electrode was designed to be movable, allowing for accurate adjustment of distance between PPC electrodes. This setup ensured uniform contact and minimized measurement errors by reducing the probability of air entrapment due to misalignment between PPC electrodes and allowed accurate dielectric property measurements under controlled conditions.

2.4. Material Characterization Methods

The processed substrates were thoroughly characterized using a range of analytical techniques and instruments: FTIR (FTIR Spectrometer, ALPHA Bruker, Germany) with ATR module, TGA (TGA Q600 SDT TA Instruments, USA), SEM (tabletop Hitachi TM3000, Japan), water contact angle measurement (DSA25, manufacturer KRÜSS Optronic GmbH, Germany), optical profilometry (Optical Profilometer model HRM300, Huvitz, Korea), electrical characterization (HIOKI, IM 7585 Impedance analyzer, Japan), laboratory convective dryer (Mettler AX60, GmbH, Germany), LPKF ProtoMat S62 (Germany). The prepared substrates were also placed in an oven to evaluate changes in electrical parameters with temperature variations. The complete experimental setup is shown in the Supplementary materials (Figure S1, Supporting Information).

Following the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) D150 standard, the environmental durability tests such as moisture interaction (number of samples 10, samples size $\approx 1 \text{ cm} \times 0.5 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$), soil burial (10 samples of size $\approx 1 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ cm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$), and water exposure (10 samples of size $\approx 1 \text{ cm} \times 0.5 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$) of YML substrate biomaterial were investigated using a physical approach by observing weight gain/loss over time using analytical balance. ASTM provides guidelines, techniques, and parameters for assessing biodegradation and electrical characterizations.^[19] For moisture interaction, all samples were placed in water. Before immersing in water all the samples were weighted. Every day one sample was taken out to observe the weight change. Before weighing, the samples were wiped to remove the excess water. The weight of each sample was recorded before (W_1) and after (W_2) immersion using analytical balance. The moisture absorbance (%) of the YML substrate was measured using the following Equation (1):

$$\text{Moisture Absorbance rate (\%)} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Soil/water degradation test was performed as per ASTM D150 guidelines. Soil/water degradation test is highly employed by the researchers for assessing degradation of biomaterials by observing weight loss. This approach is easy and most suitable to execute in laboratories.^[19,20] For the water degradation rate (WDR) of YML substrate, 10 samples were taken but it was found that after day 5 all the remaining YML samples were completely dissolved in water. The weight of each sample was measured before immersing it in water/soil (W_A). For the Soil degradation rate (SDR), 10 samples of size ($\approx 1 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ cm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$) were buried in the soil. Every day one sample was separated from water/soil and dried at 40 °C in the convection oven for 4 h. When samples were taken out from the soil, they were cleaned gently and carefully to remove extra soil. Then, the weight of each dried sample (W_B) was measured. The WDR is calculated using the below Equation (2):

$$\text{Soil/Water Degradation Rate (\%)} = \frac{W_A - W_B}{W_A} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Electrical characterization of the YML substrate was conducted in accordance with ASTM D150 for dielectric properties, a flat piece of YML substrate was placed between a capacitor-like structure, and AC voltage was applied. The measurement was done using an impedance analyzer. Measurements were conducted over a frequency range of 1 MHz to 20 MHz under laboratory ambient conditions at room temperature ($\approx 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). To examine the effect of temperature on the YML substrates, the YML samples were prepared in a circular shape (diameter of 2.6 cm, thickness 2 mm) and placed in the laboratory convective dryer, and their electrical properties were measured following the same procedure across a temperature range of 25–100 °C. The thickness of 2 mm, which is significantly smaller than the diameter of electrodes (2.6 cm), assures that the created structure can be treated as a parallel plate capacitor. Five replicates of YML samples were prepared and tested one after another under the same environmental conditions. Each sample was measured five times, and the average value was recorded for analysis.

Mechanical characterization was conducted using an Instron tension testing system (Model 34SC-2), which performed compression, tension, and flexure tests on both rigid and flexible YML-based substrates. The type of mechanical test was selected based on the substrate's properties: compression tests were conducted on rigid substrates to determine their compressive strength and point of failure; tensile tests were applied to thin films to measure the force at the break; flexure tests were used to assess the flexibility of flexible substrates, quantifying flexibility by measuring the force at the break.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Surface and Thermal Analysis of the YML Substrate

The FTIR spectra (Figure 2a) of the YML substrate, with a thickness of 2 mm, revealed bond changes and the formation of new functional groups due to oxygen incorporation. The characteristic peak at 1625 and 1524 cm^{-1} corresponds to the amide band I and band II, while the peak at 1745 cm^{-1} is a classical indicator of the C=O (carbonyl) bond. Similar findings were reported by

Figure 4. a) The water degradation rate and b) soil degradation rate of YML substrate over time.

S. Yang et al.^[21] and F. Zhang et al.^[22] The peak at 2941 cm^{-1} represents the C–H stretch bond associated with gelatine, indicating the presence of hydroxyl groups, which suggests the hydrophobic nature of the YML thin film. This was further verified by water absorption measurements, as shown in Figure 2b. When a water droplet was cast onto the YML thin film, minimal variation in the contact angle was observed over 300 s. Moisture absorption is a common issue for food-based materials. In electronics, dielectric constant and dielectric loss properties are highly dependent on moisture uptake. However, as demonstrated in Figure 2b, the proposed YML thin film exhibited negligible sensitivity to moisture variation, highlighting its stability in harsh electronic applications.

Thermogravimetry (TGA) and derivative thermogravimetry (DTG) were employed to evaluate the thermal stability of the prepared YML substrate. Figure 2c presents the TGA and DTG curves, illustrating the thermal behavior of the YML substrate over the temperature range of 30 to $720\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The first weight loss was observed at 14.5% in nitrogen and 13.9% in air, occurring at nearly the same temperature. The DTG maximum was recorded at $157\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in nitrogen and $151\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in air. The different intensities of mass loss in inert and oxidative atmospheres can be observed at somewhat lower temperatures. In the second stage, the sample experienced a mass loss of 69.3% in nitrogen, with a DTG peak at $260\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In air, the mass loss at the same temperature was re-

duced to 45.2%. Beyond $350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, under nitrogen, slow formation of a carbonaceous product was observed, continuing up to $800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Conversely, in air, the sample underwent combustion, resulting in a mass loss of 39.0% and a DTG peak at $470\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

In addition, we performed structural characterization of the prepared YML-based substrate samples. The SEM image reveals a strong linkage between the YML particles and gelatine, indicating successful blending. The SEM analysis (Figure 2d,e) and optical microscopic image (Figure 2f) of the YML substrate highlight characteristics similar to natural biomaterials, including a highly porous and irregular surface. The substrate surface features numerous cavities and protrusions, contributing to its unique texture. The observed network-like structure confirms the robustness and mechanical flexibility of the substrate.

3.2. Degradation Test of the YML Substrate

Next, an environmental durability test for YML biodegradable material is performed. Figure 3 shows the moisture absorption rate (MAR) of the YML substrate. The observed decreasing trend of the MAR graph indicates that the YML substrate can soak water initially and swell but cannot hold much water over a long period. On day 1, the YML substrate absorbed a large amount of water. However, the moisture absorption rate was reduced on

Figure 5. The dielectric constant of YML substrate as a function of a) temperature ($25\text{--}100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) at various frequencies (1 MHz to 20 MHz) and b) frequency (1 MHz to 20 MHz) at temperatures (25, 50, 75, and $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Figure 6. The variation in dielectric loss of YML substrate (2 mm thickness) as a function of a) temperature (25–100 °C) at various frequencies (1 MHz to 20 MHz) and b) frequency (1 MHz to 20 MHz) at various temperatures (25, 50, 75, and 100 °C).

day 2 because YML substrates began breaking down and could not retain much water. On day 3, the moisture degradation rate became 91.4% which suggests that the YML substrate started degrading significantly and the water retention capacity of the substrate started to saturate. It was observed that after day 5 all the remaining YML samples had fully dissolved in water, indicating complete solubilization after day 5. Table S1 (Supporting Information) shows the water uptake and dissolution trend of YML substrate under soaking conditions and moisture absorption rate.

Figure 4a shows the water degradation rate of the YML substrate. It can be observed that the WDR is non-linearly increasing over time, attributing rapid water absorption and good degradation rate (51%) starting from day 1 and becoming almost constant near days 4–5. The substrate was found to be dissolved after day 5 confirming that it has a water-soluble and biodegradable nature. Therefore, prepared YML substrate is eco-friendly, biocompatible, and can be used for eco-disposable electronic applications. Table S2 (Supporting Information) shows water degradation behavior and weight variation of YML substrate over time.

Figure 7. The variation in Resistivity of YML substrate (2 mm thickness) as a function of a) temperature (25–100 °C) at 1 to 20 MHz b) temperature (25–100 °C) at various frequencies (5 MHz to 20 MHz), and c) frequency (1 MHz to 20 MHz) at various temperatures (25, 50, 75, and 100 °C).

Figure 4b shows the soil degradation rate of YML substrate over time. The YML substrate shows a progressive increment in degradation with time, which is natural in the soil environment for the bio-materials. During initial days YML substrate shows moderate degradation as microbes begin to colonize the material. By day 4, 71.34% of the YML substrate had degraded, attributed high biodegradability of the YML substrate. This suggests that the YML substrate is composed of decomposable components like proteins, gelatine, and polysaccharides that can be easily broken down by microbes present in soil. Table S3 (Supporting Information) shows soil degradation behavior and weight variation of YML substrate over time.

3.3. Electrical Characterization of the YML Substrate

In the next stage of this study, we conducted a measurement of the electrical characteristics of the proposed samples. Electrical characterization of the YML substrate was conducted in accordance with ASTM D150 for dielectric properties, a flat piece of YML substrate was placed between a capacitor-like structure, and AC voltage was applied. Graph 5 illustrates variations in the dielectric constant (ϵ') of the YML substrate as a function of temperature and frequency. The ϵ' shows a slight increase with the increase in temperature across all measured frequency ranges from 1 MHz to 20 MHz. At 1 MHz and 2 MHz, ϵ' remained nearly constant, showing minimal variation with T as shown in Figure 5a. For frequencies between 2 MHz to 20 MHz, a slight increase in ϵ' was observed with rising T . This small temperature dependency of the substrate was observed with the increase in temperature, suggesting a significant change in the thermally activated polarization mechanism within the substrate material. However, the temperature dependency of the YML substrate is more pronounced at higher frequencies, especially at 20 MHz. The variation of the dielectric constant of YML substrate as a function of frequency (1 MHz – 20 MHz) at different temperatures (25, 50, 75, and 100 °C) is shown in Figure 5b. The ϵ' significantly increased with frequency from 1 MHz to 20 MHz for all measured temperatures. This frequency dependence on ϵ' indicates effective reorientation of dipoles with the applied alternating field, contributing to higher ϵ' values at high frequencies. The dielectric constant was found to be relatively stable with temperature and suggested a much stronger dependency on frequency. Therefore, the YML substrate showed more potential for frequency-sensitive applications in electronic circuits. The summary of trends in dielectric constant with temperature and observations of YML substrate is shown in Table S5 (Supporting Information).

The change in dielectric loss (ϵ'') of the YML substrate with the change in temperature at different frequencies ranging from 1 MHz to 20 MHz is shown in Figure 6. The dielectric loss represents the material's ability to dissipate energy as heat under an alternating electric field. The ϵ'' was found to be the highest at 20 MHz and minimum at 1 MHz and 2 MHz as shown in Figure 6a. At low frequencies, small ϵ'' was observed because higher polarization leads to increased energy storage. However, as the frequency increased the incapability of dipole orientation results in decreased energy storage and a decrease in ϵ'' . In biomaterials, the presence of moisture, proteins, and

other organic components influences the polarization and conduction mechanism.^[24] At low frequencies, ϵ'' is primarily influenced by dipole relaxation, where dipole alignment with the alternating field results in higher ϵ'' . The summary of captured dielectric loss behavior of YML substrate across different frequencies and temperatures is shown in Table S6 (Supporting Information).

The variation in electrical resistivity with temperature across different frequencies (1 MHz to 20 MHz) is shown in Figure 7. At low frequencies, the YML substrate (2 mm thick substrate) exhibited high resistivity in the $M\Omega\cdot cm$ range demonstrating its potential as an electrical insulator. At 1 MHz the resistivity of YML substrate was found to be highest, nonlinear, and fluctuating around 50 $M\Omega\cdot cm$. A notable peak around 40 °C was also observed, this could be due to water desorption, dipole relaxation, and trap states. At 2 MHz, the resistivity of the YML substrate dropped slightly with temperature, suggesting a minor temperature effect at low frequencies as shown in Figure 7a. The resistivity of the YML substrate was found to be almost constant for the frequency range from 5 MHz to 20 MHz, suggesting a minimal effect of temperature on the YML substrate at mid frequency range as shown in Figure 7b. Figure 7c illustrates the resistivity of YML substrate with frequency from 1 MHz to 20 MHz for temperature (25–100 °C). It can be observed that the resistivity of the YML substrate was sharply decreased with a rise in frequency from 1 MHz to ≈ 5 MHz, suggesting that the YML substrate became less resistive at higher frequencies. Beyond 5 MHz the resistivity of YML substrate plateaus, becomes almost constant with further increase in frequency for temperature (25–100 °C). The YML substrate exhibits the highest resistivity at 1 MHz and room temperature, confirming its insulating behavior. The summary of measured resistivity of YML substrate and trends with temperature and observation across different frequencies is shown in Table S7 (Supporting Information).

In terms of surface resistivity, the YML substrate exhibited lower values compared to RT/Duroid 5870 and 5880, which typically range between 2×10^4 and 3×10^4 $G\Omega$.^[25] FR4 has a similar value of surface resistivity to RT/Duroid, being in the range of 10^3 $G\Omega$ and 10^4 $G\Omega$.^[26] The higher surface resistivity of RT/Duroid and FR4 is a result of their optimization for high-frequency applications. The quantitative comparison of YML, FR4, and RT/Duroid 5870/5880 substrates is shown in Table S4 (Supporting Information). Both RT/Duroid and FR4 substrates display minimal sensitivity to thermal and frequency variation. Notably, the resistivity of the YML substrate, as shown in Table S3 (Supporting Information), remains almost stable across different temperatures (≈ 5 MHz to 20 MHz), comparable to the behavior of FR4.^[27]

Djordjevic et al. reported a decrease in the dielectric constant of FR4 from 5 to 4.4 over the frequency range of 1 MHz to 10 GHz.^[28] In comparison, the dielectric constant of the YML substrate shows minimal variation with temperature at specific frequencies. In a frequency range between 1 MHz and 10 GHz, RT/Duroid 5870 and 5880 have dielectric constants between 2.2 and 2.5.^[25] As these substrates are used in high-frequency circuit development, their loss tangents (dissipation factors) are 0.0004 and 0.0012, between 1 MHz and 10 GHz.^[25] Similarly, FR4 has a dissipation factor between 0.04 and 0.12, which closely aligns

Figure 8. a) Flowchart of mechanical characterization experiments, and results of performed b) compression test, c) tension test, and d) flexure test.

with the values obtained in this study, as shown in Table S4 (Supporting Information).^[27] A higher dissipation factor reduces the quality factor of resonant circuits, negatively affecting selectivity and overall circuit performance. Additionally, increased dissipation factors contribute to excessive heating and material degradation, limiting long-term reliability. Narita et al. investigated multilayer PCBs consisting of two different dielectric materials FR4 and PPE, which were characterized in the GHz frequency range. The author also reported dielectric constant and loss tangent of FR4 and PPE dielectric substrate which was found to be 4.1 and 3.6, 0.022 and 0.010, respectively at 5 GHz frequency.^[29] Similarly, Ali et al. reported a dielectric constant of FR4 substrate 3.99 at 10 GHz by utilizing Nicholson-Ross-Weir Conversion. The test was conducted over a frequency range of 10 GHz -11.5 GHz and the average dielectric constant was found to be 4.^[30] Bois et al. investigated the dielectric properties of PCB material FR4. The dielectric constant and loss tangent of three different FR4 grade boards (Nelco 4000-6, 4000-13, and 4000-13 SI) were measured up to 8.5 GHz. The author reported a dielectric constant of 3.4 to 4.2 and a loss tangent of 0.01 to 0.09 at 1 GHz. Compared to other PCB materials, the loss tangent of the YML substrate is significantly lower (0.00311) at 1 MHz frequency.

3.4. Mechanical Test of the YML Substrate

We also analyzed the mechanical performances of the prepared YML substrate samples. **Figure 8a** provides a visual representation of the mechanical characterization methodology, whereas the obtained results of these tests are presented in **Figure 8b-d**. **Figure 8b** shows the results of the compression tests conducted on YML substrate samples (diameter 2.6 cm, thickness 2 mm). As seen in the graph, the maximum limit of the compression test, 2 kN, was reached, highlighting the hardness of the fabricated material. This level of compressive force is uncommon in organic substrates, especially those derived from protein-based materials and biopolymers. More precisely many protein-based films and substrates and composites exhibit compressive strength of a few hundred Newtons, at most. This is closely related to their hydration level, cross-linking density, and structural reinforcements.^[31-33] The test results, for our YML substrate suggest that the materials in the substrates have formed a dense, cross-linked internal network potentially arising from the inherent properties of yellow mealworm proteins, including high β -sheet content and stable intermolecular interactions.^[34]

The results of the tensile testing are presented in **Figure 8c**. The thin film of YML substrate (5 cm × 1 cm × 1 mm)

Figure 9. a) Circuit design and fabricated samples; b) experimental setup.

exhibited tensile force values between 5 N and 12 N. The lower tensile force is attributed to the reduced YML protein content in the thin films compared to the rigid substrates. Additionally, the thin film's reduced thickness makes it brittle and paper-like. Figure 8d presents the results of the flexure testing for the YML substrate sample (6 cm × 1 cm × 1 mm). The YML substrate withstood the maximum detectable force of 2 kN during the test, deforming under the stress. By reducing the contact surface to 3 mm², the substrate compression pressures are as high as 667 MPa. For bone scaffolds, Zhao et al.^[35] presented a biomaterial scaffold that can withstand a compressive force of 1.62 MPa, measured on a cylindrical tube with a diameter of 20 mm. When converted to force applied it is 2.035 kN, which is comparable to the presented substrate (even though the YML substrate did not break). For comparison, RT/Duroid 5870 and 5880 exhibit vertical compressive moduli of 803 MPa and 940 MPa at room temperature.^[25] Additionally, the flexure force of 2 kN applied to an area of 1.5 cm² exerted a pressure of ≈13.33 MPa on the YML substrate. In contrast, RT/Duroid 5870 and 5880

can withstand stress of 50 MPa over a surface area of 13.93 cm² (a standard test substrate of 457 × 305 mm), equating to a force of ≈69 kN.^[25] When compared to FR4, the reported compressive strength is around 262 MPa (38 kpsi), which is nearly three times lower than that of the YML substrate reported in this study.^[36]

3.5. Validation of the YML Substrate (Flexible Substrate) with LC Circuit

Following the characterization, the flexible YML-based substrate, with dimensions of 4.5 cm × 2 cm, with a thickness of 2 mm, was fabricated to serve as a platform for planar electronic circuit integration. To demonstrate its functionality, an LC circuit was made with the use of the cutting plotter (Graphtec CE6000-60, USA) and copper foil. The copper foil was used to emulate conductive paths which are present on commercial PCB substrates FR-4. For a reference substrate FR4 was used and the same

Figure 10. Electrical characteristics of the LC circuit: a) capacitance of the interdigitated capacitors; b) inductance of the meandering inductor; c) impedance modulus of the LC circuit; d) Phase angle of the LC circuit.

design was milled onto it, using LPKF ProtoMat S62 (Germany). Mills with tips of size 1 mm and 2 mm were used for its fabrication. The design consists of a serial LC circuit as seen in Figure 9a, whilst the measurement setup and the fabricated circuit are shown in Figure 9b. Measurements were done on the impedance analyzer IM7585 (HIOKI, Japan). The measured frequency range was from 1 MHz to 1.3 GHz, however, only the regions of interest around specific frequencies are shown.

The outcome of the characterization of the LC circuit, as well as both separate components that make up the circuit itself, is shown in Figure 10. Specific frequency regions are shown to increase visibility. The difference in capacitance is 2.11 pF, where the interdigitated capacitor made on the YML-based substrate has a capacitance of 8.45 pF, while the PCB one has a capacitance of 6.34 pF, on 1 MHz. This difference remains approximately constant up until 20 MHz. The complete frequency characteristic is shown in Figure 10a. Furthermore, Figure 10b shows the inductance of the meandering structure from the LC circuit. On 200 MHz, when both meandering structures behave as inductors, the difference in inductance is 0.9 nH. The inductance of the structure on the YML-based substrate is 28.7 nH and the inductance of the PCB one is 17.8 nH. The complete characteristic, in the region of interest, with respect to

frequency can be seen in Figure 10b. Figure 10c,d shows the impedance modulus and phase angle change with respect to frequency. As it can be seen from Figure 10c, the modulus of impedance has a peak or maximum amplitude (phase angle is 0 degrees) at the resonance frequency on 681 MHz for the YML substrate, and 720 MHz for FR4 substrate. This small difference is a consequence of the slightly different thicknesses of these two substrates and the thickness of conductive lines; however, this proves that proposed YML substrate can successfully replace standard conventional FR4 substrate, even at high-frequency applications.

4. Conclusion

This research presents a novel biocompatible substrate as a prospective eco-friendly substitute for conventional PCB material for electronic circuit integration. The YML-based substrate was successfully engineered with the addition of gelatine into YML powder to support electronic circuits' fabrication. Surface characterization confirmed the robustness and mechanical flexibility of the substrate. Dielectric characterizations (dielectric constant, dielectric loss, and resistivity) were performed across a frequency range (1 MHz to 20 MHz) and over a temperature range (25 to 100 °C). The prepared YML substrates showed

relatively stable dielectric behavior, predominantly at the high-frequency range. The dielectric properties indicate minimal sensitivity toward temperature variation, confirming the thermal reliability of YML substrate for high-frequency applications such as wearable sensors, and biodegradable RFID tags. In these applications, YML substrates can be used as single-use or short-lifecycle electronics that naturally degrade after use. For the validation of the YML substrate, the same LC circuit was designed on the YML substrate and FR4 substrate followed by their performance comparison. This study showed that at 1 MHz, the YML substrate showed higher capacitance and inductance (8.45 pF and 28.7 nH) as compared to the FR4 substrate (6.34 pF and 17.8 nH). The small difference between the resonance frequencies of two LC circuits (on YML and FR4 substrates) indicates that YML substrate exhibits distinct electrical properties while maintaining performance within the acceptable range. The tensile, compression, and flexure tests during mechanical characterizations exhibited that the YML substrates are highly suitable for flexible operations. The biodegradation test showed that the prepared YML substrate was fully degraded after day 5 when immersed in water, and in soil it degraded by 71.34% by day 4, attributed high biodegradability of the YML substrate. The YML substrate is believed to be a potential material for reducing e-waste in the case of student-lab electronics kits, temporary circuits, and experimental designs. Our future work will be directed toward the optimization of procedures for more flexible PCB assembly compatibility that will be based on low-temperature soldering alloys and conductive adhesives.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

biodegradable, electronic circuits, e-waste, green electronics, substrate, sustainable materials, yellow mealworm larvae

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